

NANO FILLED POLYBENZIMIDAZOLE (PBI) FILM COATING FOR IMPROVED ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE IN SPACE

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Keywords: LEO exposure, Hypervelocity Impact, Film Coating, carbon nanotubes (CNT)

ABSTRACT

The spacecraft in the low earth orbit (LEO) is influenced by many parameters like Atomic oxygen, High Vacuum, thermal cycling, Ultraviolet radiation and MMOD impacts. It is essential to study the response of the material in these conditions because they have a degradatory effect on the material. This paper discusses about an approach to improve the structural performance of the composite structure (CFRP) for space applications using carbon nanotube (CNT) as a filler in a Polybenzimidazole (PBI) film coated on the composite structure. A 2 wt% CNT/PBI film was coated mechanically and cured in a vacuum oven. The PBI/CFRP and the CNT-PBI/CFRP coated samples were studied for LEO environment test for effective radiation shielding and hypervelocity impact test for energy absorption. The use of CNTs in the PBI coating improved the shielding performance in LEO by 35.21%. SEM analysis also showed that the surface cracks decreases with the introduction of CNTs. However, there was no significant improvement noticed in the hypervelocity impact tests for a similar value of film thickness.

1 INTRODUCTION

The spacecraft in the Low earth orbit (LEO) is affected by various parameters that are not similar to earth like Atomic oxygen (AO), Ultraviolet radiation (UV), high vacuum, thermal cycling and micro meteoroid orbital debris (MMOD) impact [1]. The material used for spacecraft should be able to withstand the effect of all this parameters throughout its entire lifespan. In the LEO, the material is generally exposed to 2×10^9 to 8×10^9 atoms/cm³ of AO, 200-400 nm wavelength of UV radiation, ± 150 °C thermal cycling and 10^{-6} to 10^{-7} torr of high vacuum [2-4]. All these leads to a degrading effect on the mechanical, optical and thermal properties of the material. Polymer composites especially carbon-epoxy composites with its lightweight, high specific strength and stiffness could serve as a potential material for spacecraft. However, these LEO environment parameters causes surface erosion, outgassing, contamination of surfaces and formation of volatile substances in the carbon epoxy composites. Moreover, the increasing amount of space debris in the LEO poses a serious threat to the spacecraft in space [5]. The debris object generally impacts the spacecraft at hypervelocity speeds of 7- 15 km/s and it could potentially destroy the entire structure if the object is a few centimeters large [6].

There has been various approaches employed to improve the overall performance of the space structure to provide shielding from all these environmental conditions like coating, insulation layers, multi shock shields, surface modification, etc. Addition of nano fillers is one potential method to improve the physical properties of the material for space applications [7,8]. Advances in research on nano materials like CNTs, graphene, nano-clays and metal fillers have enabled the use of these materials as fillers in composite materials. Employment of CNTs as a filler in the carbon epoxy composites could be a solution to improve the shielding performance of the space structure.

CNTs are composed of graphite sheets rolled to form rope like structures that show excellent thermal, mechanical and electrical properties. CNTs with its high reactivity towards polymers can

easily form crosslinks with the epoxy polymer and help improve the interlaminar properties of the CFRP material. Various researchers have worked on the use of CNTs and studied the improvement in properties of the composite structure [9,10]. The excellent thermal properties, resistance to AO, and impact properties of CNTs helps reducing the effects of these LEO parameters on the material.

This paper discusses about the effectiveness of CNTs as a filler in a polymer coating on the carbon epoxy composites for improving the shielding performance of the composite materials. It is expected that the CNTs in the coating could improve the physical properties of the coating thereby improving the erosion characteristics of the composite material.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Carbon epoxy CU125NS prepreg system purchased from Hankuk Fiber Glass Cooperation (South Korea) was considered as the base laminate for the present study. The CFRPs were manufactured using a stacking sequence of $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2s}$ by autoclave molding in a vacuum bag. The temperature and the vacuum conditions in this manufacturing process is shown below in figure 1.

Figure 1: Curing cycle of CU125NS by Autoclave molding

The CFRP specimens were then taken through a process of Atmospheric Pressure Plasma Treatment (APPT). The samples were surface cleaned using ethanol solution to remove the impurities on the surface. The samples were then exposed to plasma for 10 minutes with a power of 200 watts in a vacuum dried chamber with oxygen flow of 10 sccm. The treated samples were then vacuum dried for 4 hours in a vacuum oven.

PBI film coating with the CNT filler was done mechanically with the help of a doctor blade. A 26 wt% PBI solution in N, N Dimethyl acetamide (DMAc) solvent was purchased from PBI Performance Products. The MWCNT used in this study was CM-95 supplied by Hanwha Nanotech Co. For the film coating a 12 wt% solution PBI solution with a 2 wt% CNT was considered. The CNTs were sonicated in the DMAc solvent for 4 hours in a water bath at room temperature. This solution is then added to the PBI solution and magnetic stirred for 1 hour at 60 °C with 250 rpm speed for homogenization. The solution was then coated on the CFRP laminates as a 500 μm film with the doctor blade. The samples were later cured using a vacuum oven for 12 hours with the 1st hour at 70 °C, 2 hours at 80 °C and the remaining 9 hours at 120 °C. The sample after curing was later cooled down to room temperature in a vacuum environment. The steps to be followed for the film coating process in a sequential order is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic of coating CNT/PBI film on the CFRP laminate

The coated samples was then exposed to a LEO orbit simulation facility. The samples were exposed to the simulated LEO environment conditions like AO, UV, high vacuum and thermal cycling to study the mass loss and the erosion characteristics of the material if employed in space. The chamber was calibrated according the EOIM-III mission erosion results using a Kapton film. The samples were exposed in the simulation facility for 9 hours, which comprises of 5 thermal cycles between -70 to 170 °C, an AO flux of 6.93×10^{15} atoms/cm².s, UV radiation with 200nm and a high vacuum of 10⁻⁶ torr. The experiment conditions in the LEO chamber is tabulated in the table 1 shown below. The exposed samples was then analyzed for surface erosion using a Magellan-400 SEM analysis equipment by FEI company with a Schottky thermal field emitter at 2 kV HV.

<i>LEO Simulation Environment</i>	
Atomic Oxygen (AO)	RF power plasma with oxygen mass flow of 10 sccm (AO flux - 6.93×10^{15} atoms/cm ² .s)
Ultraviolet radiation (UV)	UV radiation with 200 nm
Thermal Cycle	-70°C to 170° C (5 cycles)
High Vacuum	10 ⁻⁶ torr

Table 1: LEO simulation Facility Environment conditions

Hypervelocity impact experiments were done for the PBI/CFRP and the CNT-PBI/CFRP specimens were studied for hypervelocity impact resistance. The energy absorption study was carried out at speeds between 2.5 to 3 km/s in a vacuum environment with the help of a 2 stage light gas gun (LGG). An Al2017-T4 grade aluminum sphere of 5.56φ mm and 0.25 grams was used as the impact projectile. Figure 3 below shows the schematic diagram of the LGG experiment setup. The energy absorbed is calculated by collecting the velocities of the projectile before and after the impact. The magnetic sensor and the laser sensors and intervalometers in the experiment setup helps us to obtain the projectile velocities before and after impact respectively.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the 2 stage LGG

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CU125NS was considered as the reference laminate in this study based on previous researches that found this prepreg system to be more strong and stiffer with excellent energy absorption characteristics amongst the commonly available prepreg systems in the local market [11]. The material properties of CU125NS prepreg system is shown in table 2 below. APPT treatment was performed on the composite laminates to improve the adhesion between the CFRP laminate and the PBI coating. This treatment improves the surface energy of the CFRP by increasing the oxygen count by virtue of formation of oxidized functional groups [12]. It was observed that the lap shear strength of a

composite material improves because of plasma treatment before adhesion of the specimens.

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	X_T (MPa)	X_C (MPa)	Y_T (MPa)	Y_C (MPa)	S (MPa)
130	10	4.85	3.62	0.31	0.52	1933	1051	51	141	61

Table 2: CU125NS prepreg properties

Carbon epoxy composites are affected largely by the environment conditions in the LEO orbit. It is hence essential to study various approaches to improve this resistance to maximize the utilization of materials in a design perspective. The use of nanofillers like CNTs can improve the performance of these materials in these environmental conditions. However, the use of these materials makes the manufacturing process complex. CNT materials if incorporated in the surface coating could help in reducing the design complexity of the composite space structure and, also enables us to use the material properties of the constituent materials to the fullest [13]. Areal density, mass per unit area, of the normal and the coated samples was measured to see the increase in the weight percent of the structure. This study helps to identify the effectiveness of this approach in improving the shielding efficiency amongst different shielding techniques. The CNT-PBI coating was noticed to have an areal density of 0.004177 g/cm³. It was observed that the areal density increment was about 1.71% for the CNT/PBI film coated samples on comparison with the CFRP samples, and was 0.01% less than the PBI film coated CFRP specimens. This difference in the weight percent could be accounted towards the inability to control the film thickness during the coating process. The film thickness of the CNT/PBI film was observed to be 42 μ m on average whereas it was around 43 μ m in the case of just PBI film.

The effectiveness of the CNT as a filler in the coating for space application was studied in this study by two set of experiments, mass loss and erosion study after LEO exposure with AO, UV, thermal cycling and high vacuum, and energy absorption capability in the event of hypervelocity impact. The PBI/CFRP and the CNT-PBI/CFRP samples after LEO exposure for 9 hours in the LEO simulation facility were used to study the total mass loss of the composite in that environment. During the process of the exposure the samples were covered with an Aluminum foil below and on the sides of the composite material. This was done to allow the LEO exposure to occur only the film coated side of the sample. The average mass loss of the samples in the LEO environment conditions was found by calculating the mass of the sample before and after the LEO exposure. The mass loss of the LEO exposed specimens are shown in figure 4 shown below.

Figure 4: Mass loss density after LEO exposure

The results in figure 4 are shown in terms of mass loss density, mass loss per unit area, to normalize the mass loss data as the size of the specimens used for the experiment were not same. The average mass loss of the PBI/CFRP and the CNT-PBI/CFRP after LEO exposure was 0.1025 mg/mm² and 0.0664 mg/mm², respectively, as can be seen in figure 4. The mass loss decreased by 0.0361 mg/mm² as a result of adding 2wt% CNT in the PBI coating on the CFRP specimen, thus

improving the performance by 35.21%. Also, it was noticed that adding CNT/PBI coating improved the LEO environment shielding performance by 50.13%. Addition of CNTs improves mechanical interlocking of the coating material and hence can reduce the matrix cracking and erosion of the coating during LEO exposure [14]. Moreover, CNTs also improve the resistance to thermally induced stress in the coating as a result of extreme thermal cycling in the chamber. In this way addition of CNTs help in reducing the synergetic effects of the LEO environment parameters on the spacecraft. SEM analysis was conducted on the PBI coated and the CNT/PBI coated CFRP samples before and after the LEO exposure. Figure 5 shows the SEM images of (a) CNT/PBI coated CFRP unexposed; (b) CNT/PBI coated CFRP LEO exposed; (c) PBI coated CFRP LEO exposed; (d) CNT/PBI coated CFRP LEO exposed. It can be seen the figure 5 that the addition of CNT on the coating reduces the surface erosion after the LEO exposure. Also from Figure 5 (c) and (d) we can notice that the intensity of surface cracks reduces as a result of adding CNT fillers in the coating. It is evident from the LEO exposure and the SEM analysis that CNTs help considerably in improving the shielding efficiency of the space structure.

Figure 5: SEM image of (a) CNT/PBI coated CFRP unexposed (b) CNT/PBI coated CFRP LEO exposed (c) PBI coated CFRP LEO exposed (d) CNT/PBI coated CFRP LEO exposed.

The hypervelocity impact experiments were conducted for the PBI/CFRP, and the CNT/PBI coated samples in the 2.5 to 3 km/s using an Al projectile. An Al2017-T4 projectile was used in this study for impact because most of the space debris is comprised of this material. The impact experiments were performed in a vacuum environment to simulate the LEO space environment, and also to reduce the air friction on the projectiles. In the absence of air drag, the velocity decrease observed in the intervalometers in the case of impact can directly be considered as the velocity decrement as a result of the composite specimen. Figure 6 below shows the velocity decrement of the projectile for the PBI/CFRP and the CNT-PBI/CFRP composite.

Figure 6: Velocity decrement by composite specimen during hypervelocity impact

PBI/CFRP specimens showed an average velocity decrement of 550 m/s and CNT-PBI/CFRP shows an average velocity decrement of 574.34 m/s. It can be noted that the CNT-PBI/CFRP improves the velocity decrement by 4.43% for a film thickness of 42 μm compared to 43 μm for the PBI film. Since the areal density of the specimens can vary, it is essential to normalize the energy absorbed by the composite specimen for a standardized comparison. The specific energy absorbed by the composite specimens can be calculated from the velocities information in the intervalometers using equation (1) given below.

$$E_{\text{specific absorbed}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} m (V_{\text{initial}}^2 - V_{\text{residual}}^2)}{\text{areal density}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 7: Specific Energy Absorbed by specimens during hypervelocity impact

Figure 7 shows the specific energy absorbed of the PBI/CFRP and CNT-PBI/CFRP specimens. The PBI/CFRP specimens showed an average specific energy absorption of 1323.27 J/g.cm^2 whereas the CNT-PBI/CFRP showed an average absorption of 1259.9 J/g.cm^2 . It can be noticed that the specific energy of the CNT-PBI/CFRP composite specimens is less compared to the PBI/CFRP specimen even though there was a small increase in the velocity decrement. This could be attributed to the velocity range the samples were impacted, hence it would influence the energy absorbed in equation (1). Another reason could be the inconsistency in the laminate and film thickness during manufacturing, which could affect the impact properties of the specimen in a reasonable manner. Hence it is safe to consider that the addition of CNT in the film thickness has very less or negligible significance in improving the hypervelocity impact characteristics of the composite specimen.

4 CONCLUSION

In this research, the effectiveness of CNTs as a filler on the polymer surface coating on the CFRP composite was studied. CNTs when used in the PBI coating reduced the mass loss, surface erosion and surface cracks in the LEO environment. SEM analysis also showed a similar trend validating the results obtained from the LEO exposure study. CNTs did not show a considerable increase in energy absorption characteristics from the hypervelocity impact study. However, the improvement in the shielding efficiency of the space structure with a negligible increase in areal density makes it a fine approach for space structure design.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by BK21 Plus Program and Space Core Technology Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea funded by the Ministry of Science, ICT and Future Planning (NRF-2014M1A3A3A02034828).

5 REFERENCES

- [1] E. Grossman, I. Gouzman, Space environment effects on polymers in low earth orbit, *Nucl. Instruments Methods Phys. Res. Sect. B Beam Interact. with Mater. Atoms.* 208 (2003) 48–57. doi:10.1016/S0168-583X(03)00640-2.
- [2] J.-H. Han, C.-G. Kim, Low earth orbit space environment simulation and its effects on graphite/epoxy composites, *Compos. Struct.* 72 (2006) 218–226. doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2004.11.007.
- [3] M.R. Reddy, Review effect of low earth orbit atomic oxygen on spacecraft materials, *J. Mater. Sci.* 30 (1995) 281–307. doi:10.1007/BF00354389.
- [4] W. Conshohocken, Solar Constant and Zero Air Mass Solar Spectral Irradiance, 15 (2014) 1–16. doi:10.1520/E0490-00AR14.2.
- [5] D. Wright, *Colliding Satellites: Consequences and Implications*, 2009. <http://www.ucsusa.org/sites/default/files/legacy/assets/documents/nwgs/SatelliteCollision-2-12-09.pdf>.
- [6] http://www.esa.int/Our_Activities/Operations/Space_Debris/FAQ_Frequently_asked_questions.
- [7] J.B. Moon, Development of impact shielding system for space structures by using hybrid composites, KAIST, 2012.
- [8] A.K. Barick, D.K. Tripathy, Effect of nanofiber on material properties of vapor-grown carbon nanofiber reinforced thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU/CNF) nanocomposites prepared by melt compounding, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 41 (2010) 1471–1482. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.06.009.
- [9] D. Qian, E. Dickey, R. Andrews, T. Rantell, Load transfer and deformation mechanisms in carbon nanotube-polystyrene composites, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 2868 (2000) 4–7. doi:10.1063/1.126500.
- [10] M.-S. Kim, A Study on the Mechanical Properties of MWNT-added Glass/Epoxy Fabric Composites, KAIST, 2004.
- [11] A.H. Baluch, C.G. Kim, Effect of velocity variation on carbon/epoxy composite damage behavior, *J. Compos. Mater.* 50 (2016) 2017–2024. doi:10.1177/0021998315598852.
- [12] S. Kumar, G. Abhishek, A. Ullattil, T. Elangundran, S. Bhowmik, S. Devadathan, C.-G. Kim, A. Baluch, Effect of atmospheric pressure plasma treatment for repair of polymer matrix composite for aerospace applications, *J. Compos. Mater.* 50 (2016) 1497–1507. doi:10.1177/0021998315594230.
- [13] G. Son, C.-G. Kim, Protective effect of nanocomposite film from the low earth orbit environment, *J. Compos. Mater.* 49 (2015) 2297–2306. doi:10.1177/0021998314545189.
- [14] M.-G. Kim, J. Moon, C. Kim, Effect of CNT functionalization on crack resistance of a carbon/epoxy composite at a cryogenic temperature, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 43 (2012) 1620–1627. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.04.001.